

Review Article

Review: Sulfa drugs derivatives antibacterial activity

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Bacterial infections continue to pose a significant threat due to the development of persistent diseases and the rising incidence of multidrug-resistant microbial pathogens. Therefore, there is a pressing need to undertake systematic efforts aimed at discovering new and effective therapeutic agents, making the design and synthesis of novel analogs targeting bacterial systems essential. The development of new sulfonyl- or sulfonamide-bearing analogs that are less toxic, highly potent, and associated with minimal side effects has become a prominent area of research in medicinal chemistry. The importance of the sulphonamide moiety in medicinal chemistry is well established, as it represents a key structural class found in many widely used drugs. Sulfamethazine (SMZ) is a commonly used sulphonamide drug in veterinary medicine, where it acts as an antibacterial agent for the treatment of livestock diseases, including gastrointestinal and respiratory tract infections. Sulfadiazine (SDZ) is another widely used sulphonamide drug, frequently administered in combination with the antimalarial agent pyrimethamine for the treatment of toxoplasmosis in warm-blooded animals.

1. Introduction

Sulfonamides are among the most widely used antibacterial agents worldwide. They were the first chemotherapeutic agents to be systematically employed for the prevention and treatment of bacterial infections in humans and certain animals, primarily due to their low cost, low toxicity, and remarkable efficacy against bacterial diseases [1]. The sulfonamide $-\text{SO}_2\text{NH}-$ functional group is present in numerous biologically active compounds and represents an important class of drugs extensively utilized in both pharmaceutical and agricultural applications. A wide range of sulfonamide derivatives has been synthesized, structurally characterized, and evaluated for their antibacterial activity [2]. Sulfadiazine is an N^1 -substituted derivative of the parent compound sulfanilamide and is a typical antibacterial sulfonamide drug. Furthermore, antihypertensive drug agents can be designed through the conjugation of sulfadiazine with antihypertensive pharmacophores [3]. Sulfonamides exert their antibacterial activity by interfering with folic acid synthesis, a vital component of the vitamin B complex present in the cells of all living organisms. While humans and animals must obtain folic acid through their diet, most bacterial cells are capable of synthesizing folic acid from simpler precursor molecules. Consequently, sulfonamide drugs selectively inhibit bacterial growth without causing harm to host cells [4].

The synthetic connection of sulfa drugs with selenium-containing heterocyclic compounds has been reported to enhance their biological activities. The presence of selenium moieties may improve pharmacological performance, including anti-inflammatory, analgesic, fungicidal, and bactericidal effects. In light of these advantages, this study aimed to link biologically active sulfonamides (e.g., Sulfadiazine, Sulfadimidine, and Sulfacetamide) with oregano selenium derivatives to introduce new classes of biologically active compounds [5].

Di-hydro folate reductase (DHFR) inhibitors, used as antibacterial agents, commonly incorporate pyrimidine, pteridine, and azine moieties within their structural frameworks. Folic acid (FA), which contains a pteridine ring and an amine group, was selected as the core scaffold and subsequently conjugated with sulfonamides to develop new conjugates [6].

The interconnection between phthalazin-1(2H)-ones and sulfonamides 1aee represents an efficacious strategy for the synthesis of potent broad-spectrum antibacterial agents. This process occurs through the reaction of key intermediates to afford the target compounds 10aee and 15aee individually. To confirm the enhancement of antibacterial activity, bacterial growth inhibition zones and minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) values were determined for the newly synthesized compounds. The results demonstrated notable antibacterial activity compared with their corresponding reference sulfa drugs [7].

By devising and synthesizing a new series of 5-oxo-2-phenyl-4-(arylsulfamoyl) phenyl) hydrazono)-4,5-dihydro-1H-pyrrole-3-carboxylate hybrids 4a–f, this study addressed the challenge of sulfonamide resistance in antibacterial therapy. Through deliberate structural modifications, the aim was to overcome resistance mechanisms and identify potential therapeutic alternatives. The chemical structures of the synthesized hybrids were confirmed using spectroscopic techniques [8].

Scheme 3

A nickel-catalyzed synthesis of *N*-(aryl)-substituted *p*-toluene sulphonamides is described. The intermediate 4-methylbenzenesulphonamide was obtained via the reaction of *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride with ammonium hydroxide. The substituted *p*-toluene sulphonamides were subsequently prepared by coupling 4-methylbenzenesulphonamide with commercially available aryl halides through the Buchwald–Hartwig cross-coupling reaction [9].

Scheme 4

A new biopolymer bearing a sulfonamide group, which has been classified as a sulfa drug, was reported. The novel biopolymer derivative was synthesized through a simple reaction between chitosan and N, N-dimethyl sulfonyl phenyl acryloyl chloride [10].

Scheme 5

In the pursuit of novel biologically active molecules, the benzylation of 4,6-dimethylpyrimidine-2-thiol hydrochloride (1) with benzoyl chloride derivatives (2–5) using hydrogen peroxide and glacial acetic acid resulted in the formation of a variety of pyrimidine sulfonyl methanone derivatives (6–9) [11].

Scheme 6

Article Information

Disclaimer (Artificial Intelligence): The author(s) hereby declare that NO generative AI technologies such as Large Language Models (ChatGPT, COPILOT, etc.), and text-to-image generators have been used during writing or editing of manuscripts.

Competing Interests: Authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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